

Conference paper

Afraid of Scooping? - Case Study on Perceived vs. Actualized Risks of Sharing Research Outputs

Summary

Fear of being scooped is among the most commonly voiced concerns by researchers concerning Open Science and Open Data. Does practicing openness make researchers more likely targets of research misconduct? This abstract describes a study based on two cases of “ultra-open” research collaboration, with the aim of comparing perceived versus realized risks of real-time sharing of research outputs, focusing on research integrity related concerns. The projects in question have produced all of their content openly online, inviting and welcoming outside participation. One of the projects went as far as allocating funding to an open membership online community. Even though making generalizations is challenging, preliminary findings give promise for the future of sharing: for example, an experiment in openly drafting a funding proposal resulted in other teams focusing their projects on different research themes to avoid direct competition.

Introduction

The current volume of Open Science themed policy initiatives, discussions, events and community action is a clear indicator of the recognition given to the need for wider access to scientific knowledge. Open Access to scientific publications is the strand of the movement with widest acceptance and most success.¹ Progress on other fronts of Open Science, most notably Open Data and Open Methods (Open Source), has been significantly slower. There are several reasons for this, such as institutional factors, funding mechanisms or the lack of established workflows. One major factor that stems from the grassroots of research, from individual attitudes and professional cultures adopted by researchers, is fear.

A study commissioned by the Knowledge Exchange network reviewed incentives and disincentives for data sharing. Fear experienced by researchers was at the top of the list of barriers; “fear of competition, of being scooped and therefore reduced publication opportunities.” According to the study, these fears plagued especially early career researchers. In addition to being scared of losing publications to scooping, they were afraid of seeming immature, thus becoming targets for ridicule. When moving up the academic ladder, the experienced threat of being mocked faded, while that of scooping persisted. (Van den Eynden & Bishop 2014)

In the academic world getting scooped means that a researcher (or a team of researchers) beats another to the punch in publishing a research finding. This happens often and only becomes a research integrity offence if one of the researchers/teams first got the research idea from the other.² Fear of scooping in the context of Open Science can be thus interpreted as fear of becoming a victim of research misconduct. Belittling someone’s professional efforts

is of course no research fraud, but it also doesn't exactly make one a shining beacon of integrity either.

How well founded is this fear of falling a victim of unethical treatment due to sharing? There is very little evidence on the occurrence of research misconduct, not to mention the effects on the victims. Because of the rarity of sharing research outputs beyond publications, our understanding of the overall social implications of practicing Open Science are also scarce. To counterbalance the fear of scooping there are widespread hopes of added transparency through Open Science, at least in terms of certain forms of irresponsible research behavior. In order to encourage more researchers into sharing their research outputs, as well as to create safe and responsible ways to do so, we need more empirical research on the social effects of sharing.

Research Question and Open Collaboration Cases

This case study aims at shedding light to the following questions: What were the research integrity related risks envisioned when starting the case projects and did they actualize? What can the international research community learn from these cases? The cases will be analyzed not as individual incidents, but as being part of a wider landscape of research cultures, social networks and enabling (or disabling) infrastructures.

The two open collaboration research cases examined here are the NMR Lipids Project (NMRLP) and the Social Media for Citizens and Public Sector Collaboration (SOMUS) project. The projects were chosen based on the approach of extreme openness towards collaboration and co-authorship. Despite their non-conventional approach towards generating and disseminating scholarly knowledge, both of the projects have produced traditional research articles, but for example in the case of NMRLP, the authorship of these publications has been based on self-assessment by the contributors (contributors meaning anyone who has commented on the project blog). Another deciding factor was that the two projects have been coordinated by Finland trained researchers. This is due to the case study being a part of a PhD project focusing on the national Finnish research integrity regulation. This caused for example the open collaboration based Polymath Project to be excluded from the cases.

The NMRLP belongs to the field of molecular physics. It is ongoing at the time of writing, with all of the research outputs available online either in the project blog or GitHub service. The SOMUS ran for two years during 2009-10, although the open online community, Open Research Swarm, that gave birth to the project, predates SOMUS by at least a year. SOMUS was a project in the field of multidisciplinary media studies and all of its research outputs were openly published online during the running of the project. Unfortunately, the outputs were not placed in an open repository post-project and are currently accessible only by request. This is an issue that I will also address in the finished paper.

Research Methods

The preliminary sources for this study are thematic interviews of five coordinating researchers from the chosen projects, together with the open online content of the NMRLP and the archives of the SOMUS.

This research is multidisciplinary both in terms of methods and theoretical framework, drawing inspiration from behavioral sciences and social sciences, especially sociology of science & technology, with strong roots in social science history, itself very much multidisciplinary in nature. Oral history has been an important point of reference in conducting the interviews.

The goal is to make the collected interview data available for further research use with an open license and through an open online repository, both in audio and textual formats. This is not common practice in qualitative humanist and social scientific research. Sharing qualitative human data is ethically complicated, but I argue that the obstacles are being somewhat exaggerated and the benefits not discussed enough. There is evidence that research subjects can be quite willing to allow re-use of their data, even if the data in question is sensitive (Borg & Kuula 2007), which is not the case for this study. Currently the biggest obstacle for sharing identifiable interview data in Finland is a data privacy ombudsman's opinion, that a so called broad consent (refers to informed consent) being a breach of data privacy laws.

Preliminary Findings

The case study is still ongoing at the time of writing. More definitive results will be available at the time of SciDataCon 2016. Nevertheless, there are some interesting preliminary observations and findings to be shared. Markus Miettinen, one of the key researchers of the NMRLP, compared in a workshop presentation his initial fears when initiating the project with what actually happened. He listed eight risk scenarios, ranging from lack of participants to scooping and personal conflicts. According to him (Laine et al. 2015)

[...] the experiences gained on open research during the NMRlipids project have been extremely positive, and none of the major fears we had before starting the project have actualized. Quite the contrary, the open research approach has proven to be an extremely fruitful as well as rewarding way to do research.

The SOMUS has gathered similarly promising experiences. Opening up research funding proposals, possibly one of the most radical and controversial ideas developed under the Open Science movement umbrella, gets back up in the SOMUS project report (Kronkvist 2011):

Could research funding generally be applied to 'open calls'? An often-used reason for a closed doors policy is that of competition. Research ideas can be stolen, and project applicants engage in tough battles for funding. It became clear through discussions with other applicants, however, that the open draft actually helped them focus their projects on different research themes to avoid direct competition with Somus. When a text is documented in a wiki, it is easy to find an author and time stamp for the text, making it uncomplicated to solve authorship questions.

To what extent these and other examples drawn from the cases can be generalized and translated to other research fields and environments, will be discussed in the final paper.

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Competing Interests

The author declares that there are no competing interests.

Notes

- 1 See for example the recent statement made by EU member states about making all scientific articles freely accessible by 2020: <http://english.eu2016.nl/documents/press-releases/2016/05/27/all-european-scientific-articles-to-be-freely-accessible-by-2020>
- 2 Many research integrity guidelines limit the categories of research misconduct to falsification, fabrication and plagiarism (FFP), but for example the *Responsible conduct of research and procedures for handling allegations of misconduct in Finland* (2013) guideline by the Finnish Advisory board on Research Integrity names misappropriation as a form of research fraud.

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